

A Study on Role of Human Resource Analytics for Organisation Development in Modern Era

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Abstract

In the current global scenario, firms were facing threats and multiple challenges. In developing countries organization development is still an emerging concept. Over the years dramatically, change was visualized in practice of organisation development. As of ambience competitive possie firms need to face menace of profitability, changing customer demand, increased competition, efficiencies, persistent challenges to perpetuate congruence among firms elements like, process, technology and strategy culture. Human resource analytics is a process applied in organization on human resource department for getting a recoup return on investment with ameliorating employee performance. Unique solution with human resource analytics results in individual of firm were Staying Engaged and Motivated, Ability to be Creative, Staff Attitudes and Hierarchy/Bureaucracy, job satisfaction, fighting obsolescence of one's skills and knowledge, speedy changing work culture. Such threats and challenges can be unraveling with contrivance of organization development in particular to Human Resource Analytics. The present research study was conducted with a sample size of 525 respondents using convenient random sampling from milk dairy companies of south India districts namely Anantapuramu, Bellary and Kurnool districts of Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka states respectively. To analysis and test the genuinity of data results statistical tools like percentages, reliability-test, and regression analysis were used. The study results as abstemious factors do influence HR Analytics process transparency, Contextomy factors do affect HR Analytics scaffolding organisation development, Metrics for HR analytics do impact organisation development and Major component for framing strategic planning in organisation development do act as parameters for HR Analytics function accurately.

Keywords: Organisation Development, HR Analytics, Strategic Planning, Work Culture.

Introduction

In developing countries organization development is still an emerging concept. Over the years dramatically change was visualized in practice of organisation development. Success of organisation is very important to survive in the competitive domestic and globalised markets. The success of organisation is credited to human resource. Without human resource no organisation can become a leader in the current scenario. As of ambience competitive possie firms need

to face menace of profitability, changing customer demand, increased competition, efficiencies, persistent challenges to perpetuate congruence among firms elements like, process, technology and strategy culture. Organisations describe human resource as people regarded as workforce for it or business industry or nation's economy. Companies designate human resources as "Human Capital". Challenges faced by individual in firm were Staying Engaged and Motivated, Ability to be Creative, Staff Attitudes and Hierarchy/Bureaucracy, job satisfaction, fighting obsolescence of one's skills and knowledge, speedy changing work culture.

Research studies were conducted on every aspect of employee life cycle in an organisation and implemented best way of possible sources to obtain best results. Due to drastic changes in the economic situations companies were forced to expertise deregulation, rapid technological and globalization e.t.c. and enhance in strategies which predict future and focus on methods to make progressive organisation effectiveness. Such threats and challenges can be unraveling with contrivance of organization development. Effective positive change influence in firm's organisation development methodology can succor business top professional employees to implement effective assessment strategies and focus on the linchpin rather than addressing firm's challenges. The OD discipline is both very successful and the subject of frequent critical discussions. Every day prime concern for organisation is to make its human resource generate its best by continuously Engaged and Motivated in work, perform uniquely and increase ability to be Creative, self boasted, make other co-Staff Attitudes boasted transforming firm to design best principles of Hierarchy/Bureaucracy, job enriched satisfaction, continuously engage in fighting obsolescence of one's skills and knowledge resulting in speedy changing work culture. Effective positive change influence in firm's organisation development methodology can succor business top professional employees to implement effective assessment strategies and focus on the linchpin rather than addressing firm's challenges. The OD discipline is both very successful and the subject of frequent critical discussions.

To handle all described Accenture companies started thinking on and working on Human Resource Analytics. On human resource department a process applied to recoup return on investment with ameliorating employee performance was pronounced as Human Resource Analytics. In general analytics is nothing but communication, interpretation and discovery of meaningful motif in data. In view of organisation effective decision making and data connected with tissue announcing as analytics. To improve business performance organisations apply a process to predict, describe and analysis, interpret business data by applying Human Resource Analytics. A critical role was initiated with HR analytics played successfully in designing, modulating, accessing and implementing. At current rate of human resource understanding and working on workforce analytics which were often descriptive, engross on pinpoint what happened and why, HR analytics as part of business intelligence provide a quick solution with artificial intelligence and machine learning latest technological evolutions in unlocking greater value from diverse areas of problems and sources of data.

Problem Statement

Tough and difficult job for any firm to achieve growth, perform top class ranking in terms of sales and revenue with utmost competition. To confront employees about duties, roles and squeeze intellectual talents for smooth functioning of firm a process requirement needed. Hence a new process initiated for which can influence, assess, affect and impact employees through Human Resource Analytics. Hence a need for in-depth study arises due to lesser or no research studies available.

Research Questions

1. How HR analytics influence components of strategic planning for organisation development?
2. What is the Role of abstemious factors in HR analytics?

3. What Metrics for HR analytics impact organisation development
4. Which Major component for framing strategic planning act as parameters for HR Analytics functions accurately?

Research Objective

1. To determine the Role of abstemious factors in HR analytics
2. To assess Contextomy factors and its affect on HR Analytics scaffolding organisation development.
3. To study various Metrics for HR analytics impacting organisation development
4. To analysis Major component for framing strategic planning act as parameters for HR Analytics functions accurately

Hypothesis

H0: Role abstemious factors do not influence HR Analytics and its contribution to success of organisation development.

H1: Role abstemious factors do influence HR Analytics and its contribution to success of organisation development.

H0: Contextomy factors do not affect HR Analytics scaffolding organisation development.

H2: Contextomy factors do affect HR Analytics scaffolding organisation development.

H0: Metrics for HR analytics do not impact organisation development

H3: Metrics for HR analytics do impact organisation development

Ho: Major component for framing strategic planning in organisation development do not act as parameters for HR Analytics function accurately

H4: Major component for framing strategic planning in organisation development do act as parameters for HR Analytics function accurately

Period of Study

Every researcher considers time as a predominant element for the purpose of study. The present research study was conducted from July 2019 to January 2020. The period of study existed for seven months where every aspect of depth study was initiated.

Area of the Study

To conduct a thorough study a suitable area and specialty required. As researcher belong to Anantapuramu district, the nearby districts namely Bellary, Kurnool and Anantapuramu districts of Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka states respectively were selected.

Review of Literature

In a study conducted by **James M. Gathungu** (2015) on organization development Interventions on the general Managerial skills of commercial bank Executives: a case of kenya Commercial bank limited in Kenya, East Africa at African continent. Using stratified random sampling method a sample of 98 different level executives from bank was selected for the study. Respective different statistical tool namely T-test used to analysis data and conduct statistical study. The study resulted as general managerial skills were good but could be improved, planned interventions were guided by schedule of activities, and few executives participated to improve performance.

Eric g. Flamholtz conducted a study on “organizational success and failure: an empirical test of a holistic model” in Los Angeles. The study was conducted on the previous work done by Flamholtz especially to develop a model of organisation success and failure. To test this hypothesized relationship, we have analyzed financial and non-financial information relevant to the hypothesized model for eight pairs of companies in different industries. The results of both the Friedman and regression analysis suggest that there is a statistically significant relationship between the development of the six critical success factors and overall financial success of organizations.

Indranil Bose (2018) conducted a study on Evolution of Human Resource Analytics: An Exploratory Study at United Emirates. The study was conducted on sample size of 500 fortune companies. The study resulted as HR Analytics was greatly impacted with the factors like Scaling up of HR as a point of interventions, adopting appropriate methods of analytics, correct identification and choice in selecting right purpose and moment of interventions and collaborative interventions.

L. Ravikiran and Kambam Vedantan (2018) conducted a study on HR Analytics – extent of its utility in making strategic business decision in IT sector in south India. The study was conducted with a sample size of 20 IT companies. Structured Questionnaire was used to collect primary data. Extensive analysis was used with the help of guided scoring for calculating empirical insights. The study resulted as expertise in HR Analytics was required, preparing organisation a strategic business associate or firm by concentrating on valuable insights of strategic Business decision making with the help of Information technology organisation.

Research design and Size of Sample

The study is based on both primary data and secondary data. The primary data was collected through structured questionnaire for which samples of 525 respondents were selected for this study from milk dairy companies from south Indian states Andhra Pradesh and Karnataka namely Anantapuramu, Kurnool and Bellary districts respectively based on convenient sampling technique. In data cleaning process 15 questionnaires were rejected due to irrelevant, unanswered and other silly reasons and finally sample size was 510. Convenient Sampling method was used for collecting Primary data. Secondary data is also been collected from database sites and articles. The collected data were analyzed with the suitable tools like simple percentage method, one way analysis of variance, Regression analysis, factor analysis and Reliability test. Table 2 depicts the socio-economic background the sample respondent.

Table 2 Socio-Economic background of the sample size

Demographic Variable	Description	Frequency	Valid Percent	Mean	Standard Deviation
Age	20.-30 Years	229	44.9	1.80	.878
	31.-40 Years	184	36.1		
	41 - 50 Years	68	13.3		
	>50 Years	29	5.7		
	Total	510	100.0		
Gender	Female	215	42.2	1.58	.494
	Male	295	57.8		
	Total	215	42.2		
Marital Status	Married	340	66.7	1.3	.472
	Unmarried	170	33.3		
	Total	510	100.0		
Educational Qualification of Employee	Post Graduate	146	28.6	1.94	.769
	Graduate	267	52.4		
	Diploma	77	15.1		
	School Level	20	3.9		
	Total	510	100.0		

Designation of Employee	Top Official	151	29.6	2.51	1.247
	General Manager	116	22.7		
	Senior Manager	88	17.3		
	Manager	142	27.8		
	Executive	13	2.5		
	Total	510	100.0		
Income Level	Below 10000	67	13.1	2.88	1.019
	10001 – 20000	96	18.8		
	20001 – 30000	176	34.5		
	Above 30000	171	33.5		
	Total	510	100.0		
Service – Total Experience	Above 25 Years	134	26.3	2.51	1.169
	Between 21 & 25 Years	131	25.7		
	Between 16 & 20 Years	101	19.8		
	Between 11 & 15 Years	141	27.6		
	Less Than 10 Years But Above 5 Years	3	.6		
	Total	510	100.0		

Source: Field Survey

Table no 2 reveals that a majority of 44.9% of the respondents belong to age group of 20-30 years, 57.8% are male, married 66.7%, graduates 52.4%, 29.6% Top Official, 34.5% income group 20001/- – 30000/- and 27.6% were between 11 and 15 years. As of demographic variable income mean stood at 2.88 indicates respondents were more cautious in particular to income level group.

Determine the Role of Abstemious Factors in HR Analytics

In the present global corporate scenario top gambit in HR today is concern of abstemious factors of Human Resource Analytics. A more data-driven approach for the purpose of decision –making process was a prediction from Analytics. Domestic and global firms consider HR analytics as pre-eminence, process of implementation was considered as slow and only a few organisations seems to apply HR Analytics. HR Analytics progress was witnessed for the past 10 years and many firms coming forward in applying in respective organisations, which results for study of abstemious factors for better transparency namely discern predicament, dossier identification, technological information mechanism, analytical prowess and endeavor approach. Table 3 depicts the views of respondents on role of abstemious factors I HR Analytics contributing to success of organisation development.

Table 3 Views of Respondents on Role of Abstemious Factors in HR Analytics

Choice of Respondent	Discern Predicament		Dossier Identification		Technological Information Mechanism		Analytical Prowess		Endeavor Approach	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Strongly agree	46	7.7	156	26.0	130	21.7	77	12.8	178	29.7
Agree	96	16.0	101	16.8	115	19.2	191	31.8	82	13.7
Neutral	150	25.0	117	19.5	107	17.8	90	15.0	92	15.3

Disagree	217	36.2	135	22.5	155	25.8	134	22.3	151	25.2
Strongly disagree	1	.2	1	.2	3	.5	18	3.0	7	1.2
Total	510	85.0	510	85.0	510	85.0	510	85.0	510	85.0

Source: Field Survey

From the above table 3 it was found that majority of 16% respondents strongly agree that Discern predicament factor in HR Analytics contribute to success of organisation development followed by Dossier Identification 26%, technological information mechanism 21.7%, analytical prowess 31.8% and endeavor approach 29.7%. The table 4 depicts the correlation among abstemious factors.

Table 4 Correlations Abstemious Factors

			Discern Predicament	Dossier Identification	Tech. Info. Mechanism	Analytical Prowess	Endeavour Approach	Total
Spearman's	Discern predicament	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	-.262**	.031	-.074	-.049	.221**
		rho	.	.000	.485	.097	.268	.000
		N	510	510	510	510	510	510
	Dossier identification	Correlation Coefficient	-.262**	1.000	.115**	.081	.050	.464**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	.009	.068	.261	.000
		N	510	510	510	510	510	510
	Techno- logical information mechanism	Correlation Coefficient	.031	.115**	1.000	.078	.033	.593**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.485	.009	.	.080	.451	.000
		N	510	510	510	510	510	510
	Analytical prowess	Correlation Coefficient	-.074	.081	.078	1.000	-.139**	.375**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.097	.068	.080	.	.002	.000
		N	510	510	510	510	510	510
	Endeavour approach	Correlation Coefficient	-.049	.050	.033	-.139**	1.000	.453**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.268	.261	.451	.002	.	.000
		N	510	510	510	510	510	510
	Total	Correlation Coefficient	.221**	.464**	.593**	.375**	.453**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.
		N	510	510	510	510	510	510

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From the table 4 it was found that the abstemious factors namely discern predicament, dossier identification, technological information mechanism, analytical prowess and endeavor approach were correlated and is significant at 1% level tested at 2- tailed. Table 5 depicts the descriptive statistics and Test of Homogeneity of Variances.

Table 5 Descriptive of statistics and Test of Homogeneity of Variances

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Levene's Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Discern Predicament	3.06	.990	1.625	11	497	.000
Dossier Identification	2.46	1.185	5.598	11	497	.000
Technological Information Mechanism	2.58	1.183	9.015	11	497	.000
Analytical Prowess	2.66	1.126	4.964	11	497	.000
Endeavour Approach	2.46	1.275	9.484	11	497	.000

The Table 6 Depicts the views of respondents and respective analysis of variance

Table 6 Analysis of Variance

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Discern Predicament	Between Groups	40.116	12	3.343	3.620	.000
	Within Groups	459.000	497	.924		
	Total	499.116	509			
Dossier Identification	Between Groups	164.341	12	13.695	12.369	.000
	Within Groups	550.294	497	1.107		
	Total	714.635	509			
Technological Information Mechanism	Between Groups	267.041	12	22.253	24.845	.000
	Within Groups	445.163	497	.896		
	Total	712.204	509			
Analytical Prowess	Between Groups	121.529	12	10.127	9.616	.000
	Within Groups	523.422	497	1.053		
	Total	644.951	509			
Endeavour Approach	Between Groups	195.154	12	16.263	12.795	.000
	Within Groups	631.711	497	1.271		
	Total	826.865	509			

The table 6 reveals that the differences between group means were statistically significant and determines how best the model fits the data. It also determines the model meets the assumptions of the analysis Alert behaviour of Companies required in dealing with HR Analytics abstemious factors namely discern predicament, dossier identification, technological information mechanism, analytical prowess and endeavor approach.

H0: Role abstemious factors do not influence HR Analytics and its contribution to success of organisation development.

H1: Role abstemious factors do influence HR Analytics and its contribution to success of organisation development.

Table 7 depicts the views of respondents towards role abstemious factors in HR Analytics and contribution to success of organisation development.

Table 7 Views of Respondents towards Role Abstemious Factors in HR Analytics

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	l	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Discern predicament	Equal variances assumed	.388	.533	-.640	508	.523	-.057	.089	-.231	.118
	Equal variances not assumed			-.641	463.690	.522	-.057	.089	-.231	.118
Dossier identification	Equal variances assumed	.420	.517	.178	508	.859	.019	.106	-.190	.228
	Equal variances not assumed			.177	456.273	.859	.019	.107	-.191	.229
Technological information mechanism	Equal variances assumed	.344	.558	1.078	508	.282	.114	.106	-.094	.323
	Equal variances not assumed			1.074	455.254	.283	.114	.106	-.095	.323
Analytical prowess	Equal variances assumed	.097	.755	1.018	508	.309	.103	.101	-.096	.301
	Equal variances not assumed			1.017	460.798	.309	.103	.101	-.096	.301
Endeavour approach	Equal variances assumed	8.430	.004	-1.756	508	.080	-.200	.114	-.424	.024
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.777	479.415	.076	-.200	.113	-.422	.021

The above table 7 reveals the t values of 0 indicates that the sample results exactly the null hypothesis which is not in our case and t values more than 0 and result in rejection of null hypothesis. The respective alternative hypothesis is selected. Hence the Role abstemious factors do influence HR Analytics and its contribution to success of organisation development

Factors Affecting HR Analytics Scaffolding Organisation Development

Firms fight among its competitors in a pre-planned way. Most of the strategy designing executed under purview of top officials who initiate involving best human resource. Planning and organizing relating HR Analytics frame work sometimes affected contextomy factors namely Rivalry mechanism, Facsimile mechanism, primeval imitation, logic driven analytics, Risk Leverage, Integration and Synergy, Optimization, firm conformation, High labor – capital ratio, High Market Revenue generation, Ingenious Orientation and firm size. Every individual contextomy factors had

to be seriously analyzed and respective framework solution to be made. Still contextomy factors create a huge impact on HR Analytics. The table 8 depicts the views of respondents on contextomy factors affecting HR Analytics scaffolding organisation development.

Table 8 Contextomy factors – affecting HR Analytics

Contextomy factors	Strongly agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly Disagree	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Rivalry Mechanism	45	7.5	309	51.5	142	23.7	5	8	9	1.5
Facsimile Mechanism	155	25.8	102	17	116	19.3	128	21.3	9	1.5
Primeval Imitation	155	25.8	230	38.3	116	19.3	0	0	9	1.5
Logic Driven Analytics	88	14.7	304	50.7	116	19.3	2	.3	29	4.8
Risk Leverage	179	29.8	226	37.7	80	13.3	8	1.3	17	2.8
Integration And Synergy	47	7.8	306	51.0	306	51.0	306	51.0	306	51.0
Optimization	148	24.7	148	24.7	148	24.7	148	24.7	148	24.7
Firm Conformation	125	20.8	125	20.8	125	20.8	125	20.8	125	20.8
High Labor – Capital Ratio	77	12.8	77	12.8	77	12.8	77	12.8	77	12.8
High Market Revenue Generation	128	21.3	128	21.3	128	21.3	128	21.3	128	21.3
Ingenious Orientation	172	28.7	172	28.7	172	28.7	172	28.7	172	28.7
Firm Size	76	12.7	76	12.7	76	12.7	76	12.7	76	12.7

Source: Field Survey

H0: Contextomy factors do not affect HR Analytics scaffolding organisation development.

H2: Contextomy factors do affect HR Analytics scaffolding organisation development.

Factor loading was conducted for contextomy factors and loading is displayed as follows.

Table 9 Depicts Descriptive Statistics for Contextomy Factors

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Analysis N
Facsimile mechanism	2.2451	.68432	510
Primeval limitation	1.9765	.83126	510
Firm conformation	2.0137	.78406	510
Logic driven analytics	2.1686	.90999	510
Risk Leverage	1.9039	.90000	510
Integration and Synergy	2.2392	.68210	510
Optimization	1.9824	.82071	510
High Market Revenue generation	2.0137	.79895	510
High labor capital ratio	2.1608	.84195	510
Ingenious Orientation	1.9157	.87238	510

The table 10 depicts the KMO and Bartlett's test of contextomy factors affect HR Analytics scaffolding organisation development.

Table 10 KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.595
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	435.285
	df	45
	Sig.	.000

From the table 10 it was found that Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was significant at 1% level of significance, Kaiser – Meyer – Olkin measure of sampling adequacy was .595 which is greater than the acceptable value .5 resulting as all the factors to be considered for the study. The table 11 depicts the views of respondents on contextomy factors affecting HR Analytics scaffolding organisation development.

Table 11 Reliability Statistics – contextomy factors

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.973	.975	11

The respective correlation between the contextomy factors will be shown in the following table12.

Table 12 Inter-Item Correlation Matrix

	Facsimile mechanism	Primeval limitation	Firm conformation	Logic Driven analytics	Risk Leverage	Integration And Synergy	Optimization	High Market Revenue generation	High Labor Capital ratio	Ingenious Orientation	Firm size
Facsimile mechanism	1.000	.741	.837	.828	.792	.783	.742	.763	.777	.735	.777
Primeval limitation	.741	1.000	.792	.793	.794	.745	.761	.824	.762	.748	.742
Firm conformation	.837	.792	1.000	.803	.812	.786	.729	.774	.750	.731	.782
Logic driven analytics	.828	.793	.803	1.000	.767	.798	.784	.787	.758	.793	.798
Risk Leverage	.792	.794	.812	.767	1.000	.801	.796	.815	.730	.741	.799
Integration and Synergy	.783	.745	.786	.798	.801	1.000	.715	.791	.772	.740	.977
Optimization	.742	.761	.729	.784	.796	.715	1.000	.808	.811	.812	.713
High Market Revenue generation	.763	.824	.774	.787	.815	.791	.808	1.000	.809	.793	.785
High labor capital ratio	.777	.762	.750	.758	.730	.772	.811	.809	1.000	.737	.767
Ingenious Orientation	.735	.748	.731	.793	.741	.740	.812	.793	.737	1.000	.735
Firm size	.777	.742	.782	.798	.799	.977	.713	.785	.767	.735	1.000

From the 12 it was found that all the factors of contextomy were correlated. The table 13 depicts the Reliability analysis total statistics of contextomy factors affecting HR Analytics scaffolding organisation development.

Table13 Contextomy factors -Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Facsimile mechanism	33.48	1342.266	.866	.797	.970
Primeval limitation	33.41	1273.601	.861	.770	.970
Firm conformation	33.52	1303.591	.869	.793	.970
Logic driven analytics	33.50	1327.802	.884	.807	.970
Risk Leverage	33.42	1251.689	.878	.808	.970
Integration and Synergy	33.42	1312.076	.881	.957	.970
Optimization	33.37	1263.683	.859	.805	.970
High Market Revenue generation	33.38	1262.599	.892	.813	.969
High labor capital ratio	33.49	1322.274	.856	.778	.970
Ingenious Orientation	33.37	1246.908	.844	.748	.971
Firm size	33.48	1310.934	.877	.956	.970

The above table13 reveals that each contextomy factor corrected item correlated depicts as greater than 0.3 indicates to consider for study. Cronbach's alpha based on standard item was greater than Cronbach's alpha if item deleted individual contextomy factor implies as scale is good and no item is really required to be deleted. All the factors of contextomy factors were in same direction as a whole H0 which result as rejecting hence alternate hypothesis that contextomy factors do affect HR Analytics scaffolding organisation development

Metrics for HR Analytics Impact Organisation Development

In a data communication of meaningful arrangement, analysis, innovation, discovery and interpretation process was designated as Analytics. Analytics depends on combination of operations research, Computer programming and statistics together resulting as quantifying performance in the current scenario. Metrics was a measuring process or progress of firm or performance in the internal environment of the company. Metrics directly concentrate on tracking a specific business process allotted from available alternative processes prevailed in the company.

Metrics in HR Analytics helps to assess failure or success, monitor and track various business processes. Elements of HR Metrics were employee statistics, selecting authentic metrics, employee and productivity ratio, integrating sources of data from initial to end stage, calculating employee values, gauging employee engagement, outcome or impact metrics, effectiveness, evaluating efficiency of the HR function, evaluating effectiveness of employee processes, promoting cultural change, efficiency and quantifying investment in one off initiatives and programs. The table 14 depicts the views of respondents on as per designation and service with respect to Metrics for HR analytics and its impact organisation development.

Table 14 Views of Respondents on as Per Designation and Service

Designation	Service	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
Top Official	Above 25 years	1.95	39	.999
	Between 21 & 25 years	1.78	41	.822
	Between 16 & 20 years	1.81	27	.962
	Between 11 & 15 years	2.00	43	.845
	< 10 years but above 5 years	3.00	1	.
	Total		1.90	151
General Manager	Above 25 years	2.06	33	1.059
	Between 21 & 25 years	2.23	22	.869
	Between 16 & 20 years	2.13	23	1.140
	Between 11 & 15 years	1.82	38	.896
	Total		2.03	116
Senior Manager	Above 25 years	1.11	27	.320
	Between 21 & 25 years	1.11	27	.320
	Between 16 & 20 years	1.07	15	.258
	Between 11 & 15 years	1.11	18	.323
	< 10 years but above 5 years	2.00	1	.
	Total		1.11	88
Manager	Above 25 years	1.71	31	.461
	Between 21 & 25 years	1.78	37	.534
	Between 16 & 20 years	1.79	33	.415
	Between 11 & 15 years	1.65	40	.580
	< 10 years but above 5 years	1.00	1	.
	Total		1.73	142
Executive	Above 25 years	4.00	4	.000
	Between 21 & 25 years	4.00	4	.000
	Between 16 & 20 years	4.00	3	.000
	Between 11 & 15 years	4.00	2	.000
	Total		4.00	13
Total	Above 25 years	1.81	134	.943
	Between 21 & 25 years	1.79	131	.841
	Between 16 & 20 years	1.83	101	.917
	Between 11 & 15 years	1.77	141	.825
	< 10 years but above 5 years	2.00	3	1.000
	Total		1.80	510

Source: Field Survey

Table 14 depicts the views of respondents on as per designation and service with respect to Metrics for HR analytics and its impact organisation development. Its respective mean, Number of respondents N and standard deviation were calculated. Table 15 depicts the Pearson correlation coefficient for elements of HR metrics.

Table 15 Pearson Correlation Coefficient for Elements of HR Metrics

	Employee statistics	Selecting Authentic metrics	Employee And productivity ratio	Integrating Data From initial to end stage	Calculating Employee values	Gauging Employee engagement	Outcome Or Impact metrics	Effectiveness	Evaluating Efficiency Of hr function	Evaluating Effectiveness Of employee processes	Promoting Cultural change	Efficiency	Quantifying Investment In one off initiatives programs	
P E A R S O N C O R R E L A T I O N	Employee statistics	1.000	-.180	.121	-.002	.023	-.056	.084	-.072	-.039	.101	-.085	-.003	-.115
	Selecting authentic metrics	-.180	1.000	.142	.188	.056	.062	-.003	.033	-.024	.036	-.004	-.053	.034
	Employee and productivity ratio	.121	.142	1.000	.162	-.041	.085	.028	.064	.071	.005	.008	.078	.033
	Integrating data from initial to end stage	-.002	.188	.162	1.000	-.111	.016	.089	.034	.093	.005	-.012	.048	.048
	Calculating employee values	.023	.056	-.041	-.111	1.000	.017	-.005	.014	.014	-.077	-.004	-.010	.040
	Gauging employee engagement	-.056	.062	.085	.016	.017	1.000	-.233	.071	.063	.095	.454	.328	-.044
	Outcome or impact metrics	.084	-.003	.028	.089	-.005	-.233	1.000	.076	-.006	.030	-.117	.031	.341
	Effectiveness	-.072	.033	.064	.034	.014	.071	.076	1.000	-.072	.029	.071	.409	.082
	Evaluating efficiency of hr function	-.039	-.024	.071	.093	.014	.063	-.006	-.072	1.000	-.104	-.008	-.036	.376
	Evaluating effectiveness of employee processes	.101	.036	.005	.005	-.077	.095	.030	.029	-.104	1.000	.081	.026	-.059
	Promoting cultural change	-.085	-.004	.008	-.012	-.004	.454	-.117	.071	-.008	.081	1.000	.290	.106
	Efficiency	-.003	-.053	.078	-.048	-.010	.328	.031	.409	-.036	.026	.290	1.000	.030
	Quantifying investment in one off initiatives programs	-.115	.034	.033	.048	.040	-.044	.341	.082	.376	-.059	.106	.030	1.000

For several predictor variables value of criterion multiple regression statistical tool was used to test Elements of HR Metrics were employee statistics, selecting authentic metrics, employee and productivity ratio, integrating sources of data from initial to end stage, calculating employee values, gauging employee engagement, outcome or impact metrics, effectiveness, evaluating efficiency of the HR function, evaluating effectiveness of employee processes, promoting cultural change, efficiency and quantifying investment in one off initiatives and programs were used as inputs. In the present study HR metric was (Y) as Independent Variable, employee statistics (X1), selecting authentic metrics (X2), employee and productivity ratio (X3), integrating sources of data from initial to end stage (X4), calculating employee values (X5), gauging employee engagement (X6), outcome or impact metrics (X7), effectiveness (X7), evaluating efficiency of the HR function (X8), evaluating effectiveness of employee processes (X9), promoting cultural change (X10), efficiency

and quantifying investment in one off initiatives and programs (X11) are predictor variables and a, b, c and d were constant. Regression equation was as follows

$$Y = aX1 + bX2 + cX3 + dX4 + eX5 + fX6 + gX7 + hX8 + iX9 + jX10 + kX11$$

H0: Metrics for HR analytics do not impact organisation development

H3: Metrics for HR analytics do impact organisation development

Table 16 Multiple regressions for consumer buying behavior based on elements of Brand

variables	Un-standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			Statistical Inference	
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig		F value
Constant	5.674	.526		10.793	.000	R = 0.916 R2 = 0.839 Adjusted R2 = 0.835	199.407***
X1	.938	.067	.266	13.976	.000		
X2	.930	.060	.298	15.611	.000		
X3	.997	.060	.317	16.907	.000		
X4	.912	.060	.284	15.103	.000		
X5	.891	.055	.297	16.261	.000		
X6	.780	.132	.128	5.908	.000		
X7	.516	.101	.104	5.128	.000		
X8	.553	.103	.108	5.363	.000		
X9	.667	.077	.174	8.632	.000		
X10	.576	.080	.132	7.177	.000		
X11	.681	.101	.141	6.728	.000		

*** Sig at 0.01 level ** sig at 0.05 level

From the above table 16, it was found that Metrics for HR analytics do impact organisation development. From the statistics it was notified that independent variable with higher level of β has higher impact on dependent variable employee and productivity ratio ($\beta = 0.997$, $p < 0.01$) is the most influential factor, followed by employee statistics ($\beta = 0.938$, $p < 0.01$), selecting authentic metrics ($\beta = 0.930$, $p < 0.01$), integrating sources of data from initial to end stage ($\beta = 0.912$, $p < 0.01$), calculating employee values ($\beta = 0.891$, $p < 0.01$), gauging employee engagement ($\beta = 0.780$, $p < 0.01$), gauging employee engagement ($\beta = 0.780$, $p < 0.01$), efficiency and quantifying investment in one off initiatives and programs ($\beta = 0.681$, $p < 0.01$), evaluating effectiveness of employee processes ($\beta = 0.667$, $p < 0.01$), promoting cultural change ($\beta = 0.576$, $p < 0.01$) and evaluating efficiency of the HR function ($\beta = 0.576$, $p < 0.01$) are exerted a statistically significant and positive influence on organisation development. The standardized coefficients Beta column, gives the coefficients of independent variables in the regression equation

$$Y = 0.938 X1 + 0.930 X2 + 0.997 X3 + 0.912 X4 + 0.891 X5 + 0.780 X6 + 0.516 X7 + .553X8 + .667X9 + .576X10 + .681X11$$

The below chart 1 depicts the normal p plot of regression standardized residual with HR Metrics as dependent variable with respect to predictor variables Organisation Development.

Strategic Planning as Parameters for HR Analytics

Every organisation to capture market share, build an image and stay stubborn by focusing on issues planning, scenario planning and vision planning. HR Analytics defines an aesthetic strategy concentrating on resources available direct and makes decisions to pursue course of action. HR Analytics extends a mechanism for process identification with perfect design, guiding and implementation of strategy suitable to with stand competition in the domestic and global scenario which every corporate need to analysis, adopt and execute it in better way. Every business firm need to work on Components which acts as parameters for analytics to function accurately namely recruitment and selection, work force- compliance, workforce-connectivity, training and development, progressive turnover rate, succession planning and performance management. The table 17 depicts the views of respondents on Strategic planning as parameters for HR Analytics

Table 17 Respondents views on designation vs. parameters for HR Analytics

Parameters For Analytics	Designation	Top Official			General Manager			Senior Manager			Manager			Executive			Total
		M	N	S.D	M	N	S.D	M	N	S.D	M	N	S.D	M	N	S.D	
Recruitment And Selection	Choice of respondent																
	SA	1.92	24	.929	2.14	14	.949	1.11	9	.333	1.86	14	.363	0	0	0	1.84
	Agree	1.89	84	.919	2.00	64	.976	1.10	58	.307	1.67	72	.475	4.00	7	.000	1.75
	Neutral	1.88	34	.769	1.97	29	1.052	1.11	19	.315	1.82	38	.609	4.00	4	.000	1.83
	Disagree	2.67	3	1.528	2.00	7	1.155	1.00	1	.000	1.67	9	.500	4.00	2	.000	1.90
	Strong Disagree	1.67	6	1.033	3.00	2	.000	2.00	1	.000	1.67	9	.500	0	0		2.05
	Total	1.90	151	.900	2.03	116	.991	1.11	88	.319	1.73	142	.507	4.00	13	.000	1.80
Work Force- Compliance	SA	2.08	38	.850	1.85	34	.892	1.08	24	.282	1.77	35	.547	4.00	2	.000	133
	Compliance	1.88	51	.952	2.18	44	1.040	1.15	33	.364	1.64	56	.520	4.00	8	.000	192
	Neutral	1.77	53	.824	1.93	29	.998	1.07	29	.258	1.85	33	.442	4.00	1	.000	145
	Disagree	2.67	3	1.528	2.00	7	1.155	1.00	1	0	1.67	9	.500	4.00	2	.000	20
	SA	1.67	6	1.033	3.00	2	.000	2.00	1	0	1.67	9	.500	4.00	13	.000	20
	Total	1.90	151	.900	2.03	116	.991	1.11	88	.319	1.73	142	.507			.000	510

Workforce- Connectivity	SA	1.64	36	.762	1.00	18	.000	1.00	18	.000	1.72	32	.581	4.00	2	.000	131
	Agree	2.10	51	1.025	1.06	49	.242	1.06	49	.242	1.71	66	.456	4.00	5	.000	247
	Neutral	2.53	19	1.020	1.40	15	.507	1.40	15	.507	1.83	23	.576	4.00	4	.000	82
	Disagree	2.00	7	1.155	1.00	1	.000	1.00	1	.000	1.67	9	.500	4.00	0	.000	20
	SA	2.33	3	1.155	1.20	5	.447	1.20	5	.447	1.67	12	.492	4.00	2	.000	30
	Total		116	.991	1.11	88	.319	1.11	88	.319	1.73	142	.507	4.00	13	.000	510
Training And Development	SA	2.00	12	.853	1.60	15	.73	1.00	5	.000	2.00	7	.000	4.00	1	.000	40
	Development	1.81	103	.864	2.06	77	.991	112	67	.327	1.73	93	.534	4.00	9	.000	349
	Neutral	2.19	27	.921	2.13	15	1.125	107	14	.267	1.67	24	.482	4.00	1	.000	81
	Disagree	2.67	3	1.528	2.00	7	1.155	100	1	.000	1.67	9	.500	4.00	2	.000	20
	SA	1.67	6	1.033	3.00	2	.000	2.00	1	.000	1.67	9	.500	4.00	13	.000	20
	Total	1.90	151	.900	2.03	116	.991	1.11	88	.319	1.73	142	.507	4.00	40	.000	510
Progressive	SA	1.94	33	.864	2.17	29	.966	1.08	25	.277	.406	4.00	2	.000	4.00	2	.000
	Turnover Rate	1.82	66	.802	1.98	49	.968	1.08	40	.267	.563	4.00	6	.000	4.00	6	.000
	Neutral	2.03	38	.972	1.93	28	1.052	1.25	16	.447	.497	4.00	3	.000	4.00	3	.000
	Disagree	2.67	3	1.528	2.00	7	1.155	1.00	1	.000	.563	4.00	0	.000	0.00	0	.000
	Strong Disagree	1.64	11	1.120	2.33	3	1.155	1.17	6	.408	.500	4.00	2	.000	4.00	2	.000
	Total	1.90	151	.900	2.03	116	.991	1.11	88	.319	.507	4.00	13	.000	4.00	13	.000
Succession Planning	SA	2.27	11	1.191	2.25	8	1.389	1.20	10	.422	1.75	8	.463	4.00	3	.000	.000
	Planning	1.99	85	.866	2.06	68	.896	1.12	51	.325	1.74	76	.472	4.00	6	.000	286
	Neutral	1.69	49	.847	1.83	35	1.043	1.04	26	.196	1.71	42	.596	4.00	2	.000	154
	Disagree	0.00	0	0.000	2.33	3	1.528	0.00	00	.000	1.71	7	.488	0.00	0	.000	10
	Strong Disagree	1.67	6	1.033	3.00	2	.000	2.00	1	.319	1.67	9	.500	4.00	2	.000	20
	Total	1.90	151	.900	2.03	116	.991	1.11	88		1.73	142	.507	4.00	13	.000	510
Performance Management	Strongly Agree	1.92	24	.929	2.14	14	.949	1.11	9	.333	1.86	14	.363	4.00	7	.000	61
	Management	1.89	84	.919	2.00	64	.976	1.10	58	.307	1.67	72	.475	4.00	4	.000	285
	Neutral	1.88	34	.769	1.97	29	1.052	1.11	19	.315	1.82	38	.609	4.00	0	.000	124
	Disagree	2.67	3	1.528	2.00	7	1.155	1.00	1	.000	1.67	9	.500	0.000	0	.000	20
	Strong Disagree	1.67	6	1.033	3.00	2	.000	2.00	1	.000	1.82	9	.500	4.00	2	.000	20
	Total	1.90	151	.900	2.03	116	.991	1.11	88	.319	1.67	142	.507	4.00	13	.000	510

Ho: Major component for framing strategic planning in organisation development do not act as parameters for HR Analytics function accurately

H4: Major component for framing strategic planning in organisation development do act as parameters for HR Analytics function accurately

The table 18 depicts the views of respondents on strategic planning in organisation development do not act as parameters for HR Analytics function accurately

Table 18 Reliability Statistics – Strategic Planning – organisation Development –HR Analytics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.880	.885	7

The respective correlation between the strategic planning in organisation development do not act as parameters for HR Analytics function accurately will be depicted in the following table 19

Table 19 Inter-Item Correlation Matrix

	Recruitment & Selection	Workforce Compliance	Workforce Connectivity	Training & Development	Progressive Turnover Rate	Succession Planning	Performance Management
Recruitment & Selection	1.000	.390	.506	.502	.432	.629	1.000
Workforce Compliance	.390	1.000	.507	.597	.544	.506	.390
Workforce Connectivity	.506	.507	1.000	.569	.447	.345	.506
Training & Development	.502	.597	.569	1.000	.533	.517	.502
Progressive Turnover Rate	.432	.544	.447	.533	1.000	.535	.432
Succession Planning	.629	.506	.345	.517	.535	1.000	.629
Performance Management	1.000	.390	.506	.502	.432	.629	1.000

From the table 19 it was found that all the factors of strategic planning in organisation development do not act as parameters for HR Analytics function accurately were correlated. The table 20 depicts the Reliability analysis total statistics of contextomy factors affecting HR Analytics scaffolding organisation development.

Table 20 Strategic Planning Organisation Development HR Analytics Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Recruitment & Selection	13.60	18.500	.739	.061.	.854
Workforce Compliance	13.70	18.442	.627	.002.	.869
Workforce Connectivity	13.76	18.332	.612	.030.	.871
Training & Development	13.64	19.169	.699	.009.	.860
Progressive Turnover Rate	13.67	18.114	.621	.015.	.871
Succession Planning	13.54	19.345	.674	.029.	.863
Performance Management	13.60	18.500	.739	.021.	.854

The above table 20 reveals that each contextomy factor corrected item correlated depicts as greater than 0.3 indicates to consider for study. Cronbach's alpha based on standard item was greater than Cronbach's alpha if item deleted individual strategic planning in organisation development parameters for HR Analytics function accurately factor implies as scale is good and no item is really required to be deleted. All the factors of strategic planning in organisation development parameters for HR Analytics factors were in same direction as a whole H0 which result as rejecting hence alternate hypothesis that framing strategic planning in organisation development do act as parameters for HR Analytics function accurately

Conclusion

Unique solution with human resource analytics results in individual of firm were Staying Engaged and Motivated, Ability to be Creative, Staff Attitudes and Hierarchy/Bureaucracy, job satisfaction, fighting obsolescence of one's skills and knowledge, speedy changing work culture. The study results as abstemious factors do influence HR Analytics process transparency, Contextomy factors do affect HR Analytics scaffolding organisation development, Metrics for HR analytics do impact organisation development and Major component for framing strategic planning in organisation development do act as parameters for HR Analytics function accurately.

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